

Engineering multifunctional dynamic hydrogel for biomedical and tissue regenerative applications

Bohan Yin^{1,2}, Monika Gosecka³, M. Bodaghi⁴, Daniel Crespy⁵, George Youssef⁶, Jagan Mohan Dodda^{7}, Siu Hong Dexter Wong^{1,2,8*}, Abu Bin Imran⁹, Mateusz Gosecki³, Arjaree Jobdeedamrong⁵, M. Afzali Naniz⁴, A. Zolfagharian¹⁰*

¹School of Medicine and Pharmacy, Ocean University of China, Qingdao 266003, PR China

²Department of Biomedical Engineering, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Kowloon, Hong Kong 999077, China

³Centre of Molecular and Macromolecular Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences
Functional Polymers and Polymer Materials Division, Sienkiewicza 112, 90-363 Lodz, Poland

⁴Department of Engineering, School of Science and Technology, Nottingham Trent University, Nottingham NG11 8NS

⁵Department of Materials Science and Engineering, School of Molecular Science and Engineering, Vidyasirimedhi Institute of Science and Technology (VISTEC), Rayong 21210, Thailand

⁶Experimental Mechanics Laboratory, Mechanical Engineering Department, San Diego State University, 5500 Campanile Drive, San Diego, CA, USA

⁷New Technologies – Research Centre (NTC), University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 301 00 Pilsen, Czech Republic
E-mail: jagan@ntc.zcu.cz

⁸Research Institute for Sports Science and Technology, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Kowloon, Hong Kong 999077, China
E-mail: shongwong@polyu.edu.hk

⁹Department of Chemistry, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh

¹⁰School of Engineering, Deakin University, Geelong, Victoria 3216, Australia

Abstract

Hydrogels have emerged in various biomedical applications, including tissue engineering and medical devices, due to their ability to imitate the natural extracellular matrix (ECM) of tissues. However, conventional static hydrogels lack the ability to dynamically respond to changes in their surroundings to withstand the robust change of the biophysical microenvironment and to trigger on-demand functionality such as drug release and mechanical change. In contrast, multifunctional dynamic hydrogels can adapt and respond to external stimuli and have drawn great attention in recent studies. It is realized that the integration of nanomaterials into dynamic hydrogels provides numerous functionalities for a great variety of biomedical applications that cannot be achieved by conventional hydrogels. This review article provides a comprehensive overview of recent advances in designing and fabricating dynamic hydrogels for biomedical applications. We describe different types of dynamic hydrogels based on breakable and reversible covalent bonds as well as noncovalent interactions. These mechanisms are described in detail as a useful reference for designing crosslinking strategies that strongly influence the mechanical properties of the hydrogels. We also discuss the use of dynamic hydrogels and their potential benefits. This review further explores different biomedical applications of dynamic nanocomposite hydrogels, including their use in drug delivery, tissue engineering, bioadhesives, wound healing, cancer treatment, and mechanistic study, as well as multiple-scale biomedical applications. Finally, we discuss the challenges and future perspectives of dynamic hydrogels in the field of biomedical engineering, including the integration of diverse technologies.

Keywords: Dynamic hydrogel, bioadhesive, nanocomposite, biomedical applications

Content

- (1) Introduction of the background about dynamic hydrogel
- (2) Dynamic hydrogel vs conventional static hydrogel
 - (2.1) Advantages of dynamic hydrogel for biomedical engineering
 - (2.2) Types of crosslinking
 - (2.3) Crosslinking effect on mechanical properties
- (3) Design of nanocomposite hydrogel for releasing multiple drugs
 - (3.1) Non-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.1.1) Nanocomposite hydrogels formed through chemical networks
 - (3.1.2) Nanocomposite hydrogels formed through physical networks
 - (3.1.3) Nanocomposite hydrogels formed through the combination of chemical and physical networks
 - (3.2) Single-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.2.1) pH-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.2.2) Glutathione (GSH)-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.3) Dual-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.3.1) Intrinsic dual-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.3.2) Extrinsic dual-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.3.3) Combination of intrinsic and extrinsic dual-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
 - (3.3.4) Multi-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels
- (4) Bioadhesive properties of dynamic hydrogels
 - (4.1) Reversible covalent bonds promoting bioadhesion of dynamic hydrogels
 - (4.2) Reversible stimuli-responsive bioadhesion of dynamic hydrogels
 - (4.3) Janus-type bioadhesive dynamic hydrogel
 - (4.4) Polymer-induced bioadhesion of dynamic hydrogels
 - (4.5) Bioadhesive hydrophobized dynamic hydrogels
 - (4.6) Cell adhesion of dynamic hydrogels
- (5.) Diverse Biomedical Applications
 - (5.1) Dynamic hydrogels for studying cell-matrix interactions in 3D
 - (5.2) Dynamic hydrogels for drug delivery

- (5.3) Hydrogels as vaccine carriers for enhanced immunotherapy
- (6.) Next-generation of Hydrogels for Multiple-scale Biomedical Applications
 - (6.1) Stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems
 - (6.2) Cell Culture platforms
 - (6.3) Multifunctional self-healing hydrogels
 - (6.4) Crosslink designing strategy
- (7) Conclusions

Figure 1 Overview of dynamic hydrogels. (a) The general properties of dynamic hydrogels. (b) Common types of crosslinking for dynamic hydrogels. Parts of the figure are created by Biorender.com.

Figure 2. Representative systems for incorporating nanoparticles into hydrogels through a) physical interactions between nanoparticles and hydrogels^[1], b) chemical reactions between nanoparticles and hydrogels^[2], and c) chemical reactions between nanoparticles^[3].

Table 1. Composition and reaction of formation of non-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels.

Method	Hydrogel matrix			Nanocarriers		[Ref]
	Reaction	Materials	Payloads	Materials	Payloads	
Chemical crosslinking	Michael addition	Hyaluronic acid modified with methacrylate groups Poly(ethylene glycol) modified with thiol groups	-	Poly(lactic- <i>co</i> -glycolic acid) microspheres Pluronic NPs	Vascular endothelial growth factor Bromindirubin-3'-oxime	[4]
	Amine-epoxy	Poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether Poly(amido) amine dendrimer	Isoniazid	Silica NPs Silver NPs	Rifampicin	[5]
	Protein crosslinking	Gelatin Trans-glutaminase	Naproxen sodium	Poly(3-R-hydroxybutyrate) NPs	Curcumin	[6]
		Fibrinogen Thrombin	Tissue inhibitor	Heparin coacervates	Fibroblast growth factor Stromal cell-derived factor	[7]
Physical crosslinking	Host-guest interaction	α -cyclodextrin	-	Adjuvant CpG NPs	Doxorubicin Adjuvant CpG	[8]
		Poly(ethylene glycol)	CD47 antibody	Bovine serum albumin NPs	Apatinib Adjuvant CpG	[9]
	Hydrophobic interaction	PEGylated fluorocarbon NPs PEGylated hydrocarbon NPs	-	PEGylated fluorocarbon NPs PEGylated hydrocarbon NPs	Fluorescence donor and receptor	[3]
Chemical & physical crosslinking	Supramolecular assembly & Radical polymerization	Aromatic of gelatin Acrylate- β cyclodextrin Acrylate phosphonate	-	MgFe nanolayer	Mg ²⁺ Adenosine	[10]

Figure 3. Structure of functional linkages cleaved by acids, bases, glutathione (GSH), reactive oxygen species (ROS), light, or temperature in nanocomposite hydrogels.

Table 2. Function, composition, and reaction of formation of single-responsive nanocomposite hydrogels.

Stimuli	Hydrogel matrix			Nanocarriers			[Ref]
	Sensitive bond	Materials	Payloads	Responsive part	Materials	Payloads	
Acid	Imine	Dextran modified with aldehyde	Deferoxamine	-	Silver NPs	Ag ⁺	[11]
		Chitosan modified with dopamine					
		Alginate modified with aldehyde	Gentamicin	-	Silica NPs	Phenamil	[12]
	Gelatin methacryloyl						
		Hyaluronic acid modified with aldehyde	-	Coordination polymer NPs	Iron NPs	Curcumin Fe ³⁺	[13]
		Poly(lysine)					
	-	Poly(acrylamide)	-	Hydrophobic ion pairing	Silica nano capsules	Tetracycline Amoxicillin	[14]
Base	Ester bond	Poly(ethylene glycol) modified with thiol	-	-	Pullulan nanogel	Polysaccharide	[15]
		Pullulan nanogel			Liposomes	Lipid	
GSH	Thioether succinimide	Poly(ethylene glycol) modified with arylthiol Unsaturated lipids	Cytochrome c	-	Liposomes	Doxorubicin	[2]

Table 3. Function, composition, and reaction of formation of the dual-responsive nanocomposite.

Stimuli	Hydrogel matrix			Nanocarriers			[Ref]
	Sensitive bond	Materials	Payloads	Responsivity	Materials	Payloads	
Acid and ROS	Boronic ester (acid and ROS)	Gelatin modified with phenylboronic acid Poly(vinyl alcohol)	-	-	Silver NPs Micelles	Ag ⁺ Vancomycin Nimesulide	[16]
		Crosslinker containing phenylboronic acid Poly(vinyl alcohol)	Zebularine	Acid decomposition (acid)	CaCO ₃ NPs	Anti PD 1	[17]
ROS and light	-	Alginate Ca ²⁺	-	Photosensitization (light) Reduction of thioacetal bond (ROS)	Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs Antibody NPs	Porphyrin IX Programmed death ligand 1 antibody	[1]
Temperature and light	Temperature phase transition	Poly (<i>N</i> -isopropyl acrylamide)	Curcumin	Gelation phase transition (temperature) Photothermal effect (light)	NIPAM NPs Au nanorod	Doxorubicin	[18]
Temperature and ROS		Gelatin Chitosan β-glycero-phosphate	-	Hydrolysis of phenylboronic ester (ROS)	PLGA NPs	Bis(2-chloroethyl) nitrosourea Temozolomide	[19]

Figure 4. An overview of the material design roadmap for tough bioadhesives. Development of bioadhesive materials involves the design for cohesion, where a combination of the polymer backbone and crosslinking strategy is selected to ensure mechanical durability in a tough hydrogel, and design for bioadhesion, where a mixture of covalent and dynamic interactions, as well as mechanical interlocks, are incorporated into the material design. The image is adapted from ^[20] (Royal Society of Chemistry 2022).

Figure 5. Diagrammatic sketch of HA-DA/rGO hydrogel preparation. (a) Preparation scheme of HA-DA polymer and (b) rGO@PDA, (c) scheme of HA-DA/rGO hydrogel and the original, bending, compressing, self-healing, and the application in wound healing. Scale bar: 5 mm. The figure is reprinted from Ref. ^[21] with permission from Wiley-VCH 2019.

Figure 6. Schematic illustration of the smart Janus adhesive and on-demand removable hydrogel as a multifunctional engineered cardiac tissue patch (ECP) to repair rat's myocardial infarction (MI). The image is reprinted from ^[22] (Springer Nature).

Figure 7. Fabrication and performance of underwater adhesion hydrogels: (a) Schematic representation of the fabrication process of the Fe^{3+} induced hydrophobization process. Hydrophilic PAM-C-M made from poly(acrylamide-co- C_{18}) was immersed in an aqueous Fe^{3+} solution, followed by a water-rinsing to obtain a hydrogel (Fe-PAM-C-M) with a hydrophobic surface. (b). Schematic illustration of the self-hydrophobization process for the formation of firm underwater adhesion between the hydrogel and substrate. The compression between hydrogel and substrate creates hydrophobic interactions which repels water away from the interface. (c) Practical demonstration (with photographs) of underwater adhesion. PAM-C-M hydrogel was detached from metal surface, while Fe-PAM-C-M firmly attached to the metal block surface. . (d) Demonstration of adhesion between hydrogel and substrate by water blasting for 10s. (e) In vivo adhesion tests of hydrogels on porcine heart with blood exposure. Adapted from^[23] Copyright (2019) WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim.

Table 4. Summary of bioadhesive dynamic hydrogels.

Composition	Dynamic bonds	Characteristics	Application	Ref.
poly(acrylic acid)/polyethyleneimine/aldehyde cellulose with N,N-bis(acryloyl)cystamine/caffeic acid, PAA/PEI/CNC-CHO/CA	disulphide bonds	Janus double-layer hydrogel containing adhesive and anti-adhesive layers; conductive properties; detachment on demand thanks to redox-responsive disulfide cross-links building the network	repair of myocardial infarction	[22]
catechol-modified ϵ -poly-L-lysine (PL-Cat)/oxidized dextran (ODex)	Schiff's base bonds; catechol-Fe ³⁺ coordinate	double network; repeatable adhesion	wound dressing	[24]
poly(glycerol sebacate)-co-poly(ethylene glycol)-g-catechol/ureido-pyrimidone (Upy)	catechol-Fe ³⁺ coordinate; Upy-Upy hydrogen bonding	double network; mechanical and adhesive properties tunable with Upy content; hemostatic	wound healing	[25]
phenylboronic acid-tethered-methacrylated chondroitin sulfate/dopamine decorated methacrylated gelatin/4-arm thiol-ended poly(ethylene glycol)	boronate esters; S-S linkages	double network; the adhesive strength is higher at higher pH	/	[26]
a micellar copolymerization of hydrophilic acrylamide and hydrophobic stearyl methacrylate (C ₁₈)/ N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide, MBAA/sodium dodecyl sulfate, SDS	hydrophobic association	repeatable adhesion at wet conditions in contact with sweat, blood, etc; long-term stable underwater adhesion; strong adhesion despite water blasting; adhesion to beating heart	wound sealing	[23]
alginate-BA (boronic acid)	boronate esters	the presence of sialic acid in the mucosa causes the formation of boronate esters between the hydrogel and the tissue generating interfacial tissue-hydrogel interactions.	N/A	[27]
PVA-FSWCNT-PDA/borax ions	hydrogen bonding, boronate ester, π - π stacking	composite hydrogel; conductive properties, repeatable adhesion	wearable human sensors	[28]
dopamine-modified 4-armed poly(ethylene glycol)/Laponite	catechol/quinone interactions with Laponite	composite hydrogel;	N/A	[29]

		dissipative effect; the adhesion strength modulated with Laponite content		
protocatechualdehyde (PA)/ FeCl ₃ /quaternized chitosan	catechol-Fe ³⁺ ; Schiff base bonds	tunable adhesion with PA/FeCl ₃ content via changing aldehyde/amine molar ratio	wound healing	[28]
benzaldehyde-poly(ethylene glycol)-co-poly(glycerol sebacic acid) with phenylboronic acid and dihydrocaffeic acid and L-arginine-grafted chitosan, CDL	Schiff base bonds, boronate ester	the adhesion strength modulated with CDL content	therapy of athletic ulcer foot	[30]
aldehyde-functionalized chondroitin sulfate, CS/gelatin/borax	Schiff base bonds, boronate ester, hydrogen bonding	adhesive strength dependent on CS concentration	surgical sealants	[31]
hyperbranched polymer with thiol groups/benzaldehyde-terminated poly(ethylene glycol), PEG-CHO	thiol-aldehyde cross-linking	the adhesive strength dependent on PEG-CHO content; the hydrogel detachment governed by the temperature change	N/A	[32]
poly(vinyl alcohol)/ poly(acrylic acid)-grafted with N-hydroxysuccinimide ester	hydrogen bonding	interpenetrating network, immediate adhesion, benign detachment upon sodium bicarbonate and glutathione	N/A	[33]
Gelatin/ tannic acid quinone/borax	boronate ester, Schiff base bonds	self-healable properties, the adhesive strength modulated with tannic acid, the hydrogel detachment upon the change of temperature	N/A	[34]
collagen-Au nanoparticles	coordination and electrostatic interactions	non-covalent interaction was formed between collagen and GNP via coordination interaction and/or electrostatic interaction, providing injectability and self-healing properties to the hydrogel.	localized anti-tumor therapy	[35]
chitosan	intermolecular interactions	hydrogel loaded with platelet-rich plasma and tigeicycline-encapsulated in chitosan nanoparticles	N/A	[36]
chitosan	intermolecular interactions	hydrogel loaded with whitlockite nanoparticles	N/A	[37]
hyaluronic acid modified with dopamine, HA/DA graphene oxide covered with polydopamine	physical interactions between HA/DA and graphene oxide/polydopamine supported	mechanical performance on par with human skin	hemostatic agent	[21]

	with covalent bonds between oxidized dopamine groups			
chitosan/alginate/fibrin	chitosan-alginate intermolecular interactions	equipped with strontium ranelate – an osteoporotic drug; fibrin for increased cell-adhesion	cartilage regeneration	[38]
chitin/fibrin/CuSO4	chitin intramolecular interactions	fibrin microparticles for cell adhesion; CuSO4 crystals to increase mechanical stability; promotion of osteogenic differentiation	bone regeneration	[39]
poly(ethylene glycol) modified with Upy moieties	Upy-Upy hydrogen bonding, self-assembly into fibers	RGD-modified poly(ethylene glycol) to increase cell adhesion	N/A	[40]
alginate/gelatin/cellulose nanocrystals	ionic COOH/Zn ²⁺ supported with covalent amide bonds	N/A	bone regeneration	[41]
hyaluronic acid/gelatin/CNC-cationically modified	ionic interactions	N/A	bone regeneration	[42]

Figure 8 Highlighted examples of fundamental studies about cell-ECM interactions in the three-dimensional network. (a) Enhanced mechanosensing of stem cells in tunable ligand binding constant in host-guest crosslinked hyaluronic acid hydrogels. The figure is reprinted from Ref. [43] with permission from Springer Nature. (b) The deposition and remodeling of local nascent proteins by stem cells in the dynamic hydrogel network is highly relevant for later stage regulation of mechanosensing and differentiation. The figure is reprinted from Ref. [44] with permission from Springer Nature. (c) The regulation of chromatin state accessibility in cancers by hydrogel stiffnesses. The figure is reprinted from Ref. [45] with permission from Springer Nature.

Figure 9 Controlled delivery of drugs for biomedical applications by injectable hydrogels. (a) A decellularized ECM from the porcine heart in HA-based hydrogel for the delivery of therapeutics, exosomes and induced pluripotent stem cells for treating myocardial infarction. The figure is reprinted from Ref. ^[46] with permission from Springer Nature. (b) An injectable nanocomposite hydrogel for slow release of receptor-binding domain subunit vaccine of SARS-CoV-2 to effectively elicit neutralizing antibody responses. The figure is reprinted from Ref. ^[47] with permission from Wiley-VCH.

Figure 10 Recent advances in hydrogel-based vaccines to elicit immunotherapy for cancer. (a) Hyaluronic acid hydrogel for controlled release CAR T cells and anti-PDL1-conjugated platelets to suppress tumor recurrence post-surgery. The figure is reprinted from Ref. [48] with permission from Springer Nature. (b) Injectable alginate cryogel sponge for delivering irradiated B16-F10 cells and DC-activating factors for long-term immunomodulation. The figure is reprinted from Ref. [49] with permission from Springer Nature. (c) Dynamic HA hydrogel for stabilizing and

controlled delivering RNA nanovaccines for durable cancer immunotherapy. The figure is reprinted from Ref. [50] with permission from Springer Nature.

Figure 11 Four main categories of next-generation of dynamic hydrogels to develop multiple-scale applications.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the project MEBioSys with reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634, co-funded by the ERDF as part of the MŠMT, and the National Science Centre, Poland (Project Numbers: UMO-2018/30/E/ST5/00576 and UMO-2019/35/D/ST4/00862). S.H.D.W. acknowledges the Start-up Funding (1-ZVRY) from the Department of Biomedical Engineering and Start-up Fund for RAPs under the Strategic Hiring Scheme (1-BD8Q), the Hong Kong Polytechnic University (PolyU, University Grant Council), and PolyU Projects of RISports (1-CD5P) for supporting this work.

References

- [1] M. Ding, Y. Fan, Y. Lv, J. Liu, N. Yu, D. Kong, H. Sun, J. Li, *Acta Biomaterialia* **2022**, 149, 334.
- [2] Y. Liang, K. L. Kiick, *Biomacromolecules* **2016**, 17, 601.
- [3] W. Wang, H. Song, J. Zhang, P. Li, C. Li, C. Wang, D. Kong, Q. Zhao, *Journal of Controlled Release* **2015**, 203, 57.
- [4] Y. Liu, F. Zhang, L. Long, J. Li, Z. Liu, C. Hu, X. Chen, X. Zan, J. Xu, Y. Wang, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2022**, 433, 133671.
- [5] J. Wang, B. Li, X. Pu, X. Wang, R. C. Cooper, Q. Gui, H. Yang, *ACS applied materials & interfaces* **2020**, 12, 10202.
- [6] R. A. Bini, M. F. Silva, L. C. Varanda, M. A. da Silva, C. A. Dreiss, *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* **2017**, 157, 191.
- [7] H. Awada, D. Long, Z. Wang, M. Hwang, K. Kim, Y. Wang, *Biomaterials* **2017**, 125, 65.
- [8] X. Dong, A. Yang, Y. Bai, D. Kong, F. Lv, *Biomaterials* **2020**, 230, 119659.
- [9] A. Yang, S. Sheng, Y. Bai, G. Xing, X. Yu, D. Zhu, L. Mei, X. Dong, F. Lv, *Acta Biomaterialia* **2022**, 153, 124.
- [10] H. Kang, M. Kim, Q. Feng, S. Lin, K. Wei, R. Li, C. J. Choi, T.-H. Kim, G. Li, J.-M. Oh, *Biomaterials* **2017**, 149, 12.
- [11] C. Hu, L. Long, J. Cao, S. Zhang, Y. Wang, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2021**, 411, 128564.
- [12] Q. Yao, Y. Liu, Y. Pan, Y. Li, L. Xu, Y. Zhong, W. Wang, J. Zuo, H. Yu, Z. Lv, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* **2022**, 607, 1500.
- [13] S. Shen, D. Fan, Y. Yuan, X. Ma, J. Zhao, J. Yang, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2021**, 426, 130610.

- [14] A. Jobdeedamrong, M. Theerasilp, N. Wongsuwan, N. Nasongkla, D. Crespy, *Chemical Communications* **2020**, 56, 12725.
- [15] Y. Sekine, Y. Moritani, T. Ikeda-Fukazawa, Y. Sasaki, K. Akiyoshi, *Advanced healthcare materials* **2012**, 1, 722.
- [16] Y. Wang, Y. Wu, L. Long, L. Yang, D. Fu, C. Hu, Q. Kong, Y. Wang, *ACS applied materials & interfaces* **2021**, 13, 33584.
- [17] H. Ruan, Q. Hu, D. Wen, Q. Chen, G. Chen, Y. Lu, J. Wang, H. Cheng, W. Lu, Z. Gu, *Advanced Materials* **2019**, 31, 1806957.
- [18] S. Jiang, K. Wang, Y. Dai, X. Zhang, F. Xia, *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering* **2019**, 304, 1900087.
- [19] S. Chen, Q. Qiu, D. Wang, D. She, B. Yin, G. Gu, M. Chai, D. N. Heo, H. He, J. Wang, *Journal of Controlled Release* **2022**, 349, 565.
- [20] H. Montazerian, E. Davoodi, A. Baidya, M. Badv, R. Haghniaz, A. Dalili, A. S. Milani, M. Hoorfar, N. Annabi, A. Khademhosseini, P. S. Weiss, *Chem Soc Rev* **2022**, 51, 9127.
- [21] Y. P. Liang, X. Zhao, T. L. Hu, B. J. Chen, Z. H. Yin, P. X. Ma, B. L. Guo, *Small* **2019**, 15.
- [22] Y. He, Q. Li, P. Chen, Q. Duan, J. Zhan, X. Cai, L. Wang, H. Hou, X. Qiu, *Nat Commun* **2022**, 13, 7666.
- [23] L. Han, M. H. Wang, L. O. Prieto-Lopez, X. Deng, J. X. Cui, *Adv Funct Mater* **2020**, 30.
- [24] S. D. Li, N. Chen, X. P. Li, Y. Li, Z. P. Xie, Z. Y. Ma, J. Zhao, X. Hou, X. B. Yuan, *Adv Funct Mater* **2020**, 30.
- [25] X. Zhao, Y. P. Liang, Y. Huang, J. H. He, Y. Han, B. L. Guo, *Adv Funct Mater* **2020**, 30.
- [26] H. Fu, C. G. Yu, X. D. Li, H. Y. Bao, B. Zhang, Z. J. Chen, Z. J. Zhang, *J Mater Chem B* **2021**, 9, 10003.
- [27] S. H. Hong, M. Shin, E. Park, J. H. Ryu, J. A. Burdick, H. Lee, *Adv Funct Mater* **2020**, 30.
- [28] M. H. Liao, P. B. Wan, J. R. Wen, M. Gong, X. X. Wu, Y. G. Wang, R. Shi, L. Q. Zhang, *Adv Funct Mater* **2017**, 27.
- [29] Y. Liu, H. Meng, S. Konst, R. Sarmiento, R. Rajachar, B. P. Lee, *Acs Appl Mater Inter* **2014**, 6, 16982.
- [30] Y. P. Liang, M. Li, Y. T. Yang, L. P. Qiao, H. R. Xu, B. L. Guo, *Acs Nano* **2022**, 16, 3194.
- [31] L. Zhou, C. Dai, L. Fan, Y. H. Jiang, C. Liu, Z. N. Zhou, P. F. Guan, Y. Tian, J. Xing, X. J. Li, Y. A. Luo, P. Yu, C. Y. Ning, G. X. Tan, *Adv Funct Mater* **2021**, 31.
- [32] Y. F. Zhang, X. J. Li, G. H. Bai, W. Wei, X. Y. Liu, *J Mater Chem B* **2021**, 9, 5818.
- [33] X. Y. Chen, H. Yuk, J. J. Wu, C. S. Nabzdyk, X. H. Zhao, *P Natl Acad Sci USA* **2020**, 117, 15497.
- [34] X. C. Kang, P. F. Guan, C. R. Xiao, C. Liu, Y. J. Guan, Y. Y. Lin, Y. Tian, K. Y. Ren, Y. T. Huang, R. M. Fu, C. Y. Ning, L. Fan, G. X. Tan, L. Zhou, *Adv Healthc Mater* **2023**.
- [35] R. T. Xing, K. Liu, T. F. Jiao, N. Zhang, K. Ma, R. Y. Zhang, Q. L. Zou, G. H. Ma, X. H. Yan, *Adv Mater* **2016**, 28, 3669.
- [36] T. R. Nimal, G. Baranwal, M. C. Bavya, R. Biswas, R. Jayakumar, *Acs Appl Mater Inter* **2016**, 8, 22074.
- [37] N. S. M. Pillai, K. Eswar, S. Amirthalingam, U. Mony, P. K. Varma, R. Jayakumar, *Acs Appl Bio Mater* **2019**, 2, 865.

- [38] S. Deepthi, A. A. A. Gafoor, A. Sivashanmugam, S. V. Nair, R. Jayakumar, *J Mater Chem B* **2016**, 4, 4092.
- [39] A. Kumar, A. Sivashanmugam, S. Deepthi, J. D. Bumgardner, S. V. Nair, R. Jayakumar, *Carbohydr Polym* **2016**, 140, 144.
- [40] M. Diba, S. Spaans, S. I. S. Hendrikse, M. M. C. Bastings, M. J. G. Schotman, J. F. van Sprang, D. J. Wu, F. J. M. Hoeben, H. M. Janssen, P. Y. W. Dankers, *Adv Mater* **2021**, 33.
- [41] K. Wang, K. C. Nune, R. D. K. Misra, *Acta Biomater* **2016**, 36, 143.
- [42] C. W. Damouny, P. Martin, G. Vasilyev, R. Vilensky, R. Fadul, I. Redenski, S. Srouji, E. Zussman, *Biomacromolecules* **2022**, 23, 3222.
- [43] B. Yang, K. Wei, C. Loebel, K. Zhang, Q. Feng, R. Li, S. H. D. Wong, X. Xu, C. Lau, X. Chen, *Nature Communications* **2021**, 12, 3514.
- [44] C. Loebel, R. L. Mauck, J. A. Burdick, *Nature materials* **2019**, 18, 883.
- [45] R. S. Stowers, A. Shcherbina, J. Israeli, J. J. Gruber, J. Chang, S. Nam, A. Rabiee, M. N. Teruel, M. P. Snyder, A. Kundaje, *Nature biomedical engineering* **2019**, 3, 1009.
- [46] D. Zhu, Z. Li, K. Huang, T. G. Caranasos, J. S. Rossi, K. Cheng, *Nature communications* **2021**, 12, 1412.
- [47] G. A. Roth, E. C. Gale, M. Alcántara-Hernández, W. Luo, E. Axpe, R. Verma, Q. Yin, A. C. Yu, H. Lopez Hernandez, C. L. Maikawa, *Acs Central Sci* **2020**, 6, 1800.
- [48] Q. Hu, H. Li, E. Archibong, Q. Chen, H. Ruan, S. Ahn, E. Dukhovlina, Y. Kang, D. Wen, G. Dotti, *Nature biomedical engineering* **2021**, 5, 1038.
- [49] S. A. Bencherif, R. Warren Sands, O. A. Ali, W. A. Li, S. A. Lewin, T. M. Braschler, T.-Y. Shih, C. S. Verbeke, D. Bhatta, G. Dranoff, *Nature communications* **2015**, 6, 7556.
- [50] F. Jia, W. Huang, Y. Yin, Y. Jiang, Q. Yang, H. Huang, G. Nie, H. Wang, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2023**, 33, 2204636.